

NONSURGICAL PAPILLA RECONSTRUCTION USING INJECTABLE PLATELET RICH FIBRIN

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ABSTRACT

Background: Loss of interdental papilla, especially in the aesthetic maxillary anterior region, poses functional, phonetic, and aesthetic concerns. Injectable Platelet-Rich Fibrin (i-PRF), a second-generation autologous biomaterial, has shown potential in enhancing soft tissue regeneration. **Aims:** To clinically evaluate the efficacy of i-PRF in reconstructing interdental papillae using a minimally invasive technique. **Settings and Design:** A prospective clinical investigation was conducted on patients reporting to the Department of Periodontology. **Materials and Methods:** Four systemically healthy patients aged 18–45 years with 12 Class I/II papillary-deficient sites were selected. Following oral prophylaxis, i-PRF was prepared using low-speed centrifugation and injected at the papillary sites. Clinical parameters including CP-PT distance, percentage papillary fill, Modified Gingival Index (MGI), probing depth, and Contour of interdental papilla (according to Nordland and Tarnow's classification) were assessed at baseline, 1 month, and 3 months. **Statistical Analysis:** Paired t-tests were employed for intra-group comparisons. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant. **Results:** By 3 months, 4 sites showed complete (100%) fill, with a significant reduction in CP-PT distance and improvement in MGI ($p = 0.002$). No significant changes in probing depth were observed. **Conclusions:** i-PRF is a safe, effective, and minimally invasive alternative for interdental papilla reconstruction, offering promising aesthetic outcomes.

Keywords: Injectable Platelet-Rich Fibrin, Interdental Papilla, Black Triangles, Papillary Fill, Aesthetic Dentistry, Regenerative Dentistry, Minimally Invasive Therapy.

Introduction

The reconstruction of interdental papilla remains a significant challenge in periodontal and esthetic dentistry due to the complex anatomy and limited vascularity of the papillary region. Loss of papilla, particularly in the maxillary anterior region, leads to esthetic, functional, and phonetic issues.¹ It often results from periodontal disease, malocclusion, or trauma.

Traditional surgical techniques like connective tissue grafts¹ and pedicle flaps² have shown limited predictability and involve additional donor site morbidity. Non-invasive options, such as hyaluronic acid injections,³ have demonstrated some success.

Recent advances have focused on biomaterials like Injectable Platelet-Rich Fibrin (i-PRF), a second-generation autologous platelet concentrate derived via low-speed centrifugation. i-PRF releases key growth factors—PDGF, TGF- β , and IGF-1—over time, promoting fibroblast activity and tissue regeneration.⁵ Unlike conventional grafting, i-PRF is less invasive, eliminates the need for donor tissue, reduces post-operative discomfort, and enhances soft tissue healing. It is easy to prepare, biocompatible, and entirely autologous.

The purpose of this study is to clinically evaluate the efficacy of injectable platelet-rich fibrin in the reconstruction of interdental papilla using a minimally invasive approach.

Materials and Methods

The study population was selected from the Outpatient Department of Periodontology of the institute. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Ethical Committee of the Institute before the initiation of the study. The Patients were screened for black triangles through clinical evaluation.

The inclusion criteria involved systemically healthy subjects aged between 18–45 years, irrespective of gender, exhibiting good oral hygiene; presence of at least one papillary-deficient site in the upper anterior region classified as Class I or Class II according to Nordland and Tarnow's classification; patient-reported complaint of food lodgment or esthetic concern due to open gingival embrasures; presence of an adequate band of attached gingiva at the selected site with minimal probing depth (≤ 3 mm).

Patients having gingival recession, presence of open contacts, interdental spacing, crowding, caries, proximal restorations, fixed prosthesis, or any orthodontic appliances, history of periodontal surgical therapy within the past 6 months; patients with systemic illness, including pregnant female patients; and individuals with a history of tobacco use in any form were excluded from the study.

Patients fulfilling the inclusion and exclusion criteria were explained about the study design and the procedure with its possible outcome. Subjects were also informed and explained about the study duration along with regular follow up visits at 1 month and 3 months. Subjects who agreed were included in the study and informed written consent was obtained.

Treatment Protocol: The treatment protocol was divided into 3 phases: the pre-operative phase, the injection phase and the follow up phase.

In the pre-operative phase, initial periodontal therapy including full mouth supragingival scaling and subgingival debridement was performed, and patients were subjected to blood investigations which included complete blood count.

After 4 weeks, re-evaluation was performed, and patients with deficient papilla site/sites fulfilling the inclusion criteria were recalled, scheduled for the injection phase after 1 week.

At the injection visit (Baseline), before attempting to inject, Clinical photographs and all clinical parameters including gingival index, probing pocket depth, contour of Interdental papilla (based on Nordland and Tarnow classification), Clinical measurement (CP-PT Distance): Distance from the CP to papillary tip (PT) using Gutta Percha points and Vernier Caliper and Percentage Papillary Fill (%) were recorded.

i-PRF for the study was obtained as suggested by Choukroun et al⁶ prior to the commencement of the non-surgical procedure.

Injectable platelet-rich fibrin procurement: For the preparation of i-PRF, 10 ml of intravenous blood was withdrawn from antecubital region and was centrifuged using plastic tubes (without any additives) in a centrifuge at 700 rpm for 3 min. Subsequently, the tubes were removed and the top most yellow-orange colored liquid attained was injectable PRF (i-PRF) (Figure 1). Obtained i-PRF was filled in the insulin syringes which becomes ready to use at the desired site.

Figure 1: Procurement of Injectable Platelet Rich Fibrin (I-PRF)

Injection technique: In all the ten sites with loss of interdental papilla [Figures 2a, 3a and 4a], local anesthesia (2% lignocaine with 1:80000 adrenaline) was obtained using infiltration technique. Once adequate anesthesia was obtained, the needle of the insulin syringe filled with i-PRF was inserted 2-3 mm apical to the tip of the interdental papilla and directed coronally with an angulation of 45° to the long axis of the tooth, and the bevel directed apically [Figures 2d]. Then, the papilla was lightly moulded in an incisal direction for 1 minute using gauze.

The patients were instructed not to brush on the day of treatment, resume oral hygiene the day after using a soft toothbrush coronal to the gingival margin and prevent the use of interdental aids at the treated region. Patients were asked to visit for follow-up 1 and 3 months after the procedure, wherein the clinical parameters were recorded [Figures 2e, 2f, 3b and 4b].

CASE 1

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 2: (a) Preoperative view showing interdentary papillary loss
(b) and (c) Measurement of CP-PT distance between 11 and 12. (d) i-PRF injection
(e) 1 month post injection view and Measurement of CP-PT distance
(f) 3 months post injection

CASE 2

Figure 3: (a) Preoperative view showing interdentary papillary loss
(b) 3 months post injection

CASE 3

Figure 4: (a) Preoperative view showing interdental papillary loss

(b) 3 months post injection

Results

A total of 12 papillary sites were evaluated across 4 participants (2 males and 2 females) aged 20 to 35 years, with a mean age of 30.33 ± 8.5 years.

As shown in Table 1, the mean values of the Modified Gingival Index (MGI) at baseline were significantly higher compared to those at 3 months. The mean difference was 0.5, which was statistically significant ($p = 0.002$), indicating improvement in gingival condition over time.

The mean difference analysis of probeable probing depth is presented in Table 2. Although a slight increase in mean probing depth was observed from baseline to 3 months (mean difference = 0.125 mm), the change was not statistically significant ($p = 0.432$), indicating overall stability in probing depth throughout the study period.

Assessment of changes in papillary contour according to Nordland and Tarnow's classification revealed progressive improvement over time (Table 3). At baseline, 7 sites were classified as Class I, 5 sites as Class II, and none were normal. At 1 month, 10 sites were Class I and 2 were Class II. By 3 months, 8 sites were Class I, and 4 sites had achieved a normal papillary contour, with no sites remaining in Class II.

The measurements of the CP-PT distance and corresponding percentage of papillary fill are shown in Table 4. The measurements of the CP-PT distance and corresponding percentage of papillary fill are shown in Table 4. At baseline, the CP-PT distance ranged from 2 mm to 4 mm. Progressive reduction in CP-PT distance was observed at 1 and 3 months. By 3 months, all sites showed a decrease in CP-PT distance, with 3 sites achieving complete fill (0 mm).

On clinical examination, 4 sites exhibited 100% papillary fill, 3 sites showed 75% fill, 4 sites demonstrated 66.66% fill, and 1 site showed 50% fill at the end of 3 months, indicating appreciable and consistent improvement in papillary volume[Table 4].

Table 1: Change in Mean \pm SD of Modified Gingival Index at Different Time Intervals

Time Interval	Differences in Mean \pm SD	p-value
Baseline- 1 month	0.44 \pm 0.51	<u>0.004</u>
1 Month- 3 months	0.06 \pm 0.25	0.333
Baseline- 3 Months	0.5 \pm 0.52	<u>0.002</u>

If p-value is <0.05 then it is statistically significant.

Time Interval	Mean difference \pm SD	p-value
Baseline- 1 month	-0.13 \pm 0.81	0.544
1 Month- 3 months	0.13 \pm 0.5	0.333
Baseline- 3 Months	0 \pm 0.73	1

Table 2: Change in Mean \pm SD of Probeable Probing Depth at Different Time Intervals

Table 3: Comparison of **Contour of Interdental Papilla** according to Nordland and Tarnow's classification at different time intervals.

Time Interval	No of Sites	Class I	Class II	Normal
Baseline	12	7	5	0
1 Month	12	10	2	0
3 Months	12	8	0	4

Table 4: Measurement of CP-PT Distance and Percentage Papillary Fill

Patients	Sites	Teeth	CP-PT Distance			Percentage Papillary fill (%) at 3 months
			BASELINE	1 MONTH	3 MONTHS	
1	1	21-11	4	2	1	75
	2	11-12	3	2	1	66.66
	3	12-13	2	1	0	100
	4	21-22	4	3	1	75
	5	22-23	3	2	1	66.66
2	6	11-12	3	2	1	66.66
	7	12-13	2	1	0	100
3	8	11-12	2	1	0	100
	9	22-23	3	1	0	100
4	10	11-21	4	3	2	50
	11	11-12	3	2	1	66.66
	12	21-22	4	3	1	75

$$\text{Percentage Papillary fill (\%)} = \frac{\text{Baseline} - 3 \text{ months}}{\text{Baseline}} \times 100$$

CP-PT Distance – Distance from Contact point to papillary tip

Discussion

The interdental papilla plays a crucial role in maintaining gingival aesthetics, phonetics, and preventing food impaction. Its loss, especially in the anterior maxillary region, often leads to the formation of “black triangles,” which pose both cosmetic and functional challenges.⁷ This loss, frequently occurring as a consequence of periodontal procedures, has been extensively reported in scientific literature due to its impact on patient satisfaction and clinical outcomes.

Aesthetic concerns arising from the loss of interdental papilla, particularly after periodontal surgeries, have been widely documented in the literature. Although various surgical approaches have been proposed to address this issue, they are often invasive and yield inconsistent results due to the anatomical complexity and limited vascularity of the interdental area. For instance, Jaiswal et al.⁸ and Carnio J¹ have utilized subepithelial connective tissue grafts in combination with coronally advanced flaps to reconstruct dental papillae in patients with Nordland and Tarnow’s Class I and II deficiencies. Their studies reported notable improvements at both 6- and 12-month follow-ups. However, due to the invasive and traumatic nature of such procedures, there is a growing need to explore safer, minimally invasive alternatives for papilla reconstruction.

Noninvasive and biocompatible options like commercially available hyaluronic acid (HA) gel offer a potential alternative to traditional surgical methods for papilla reconstruction. However, these treatments can be costly and may necessitate multiple sessions. In a 2013 study, Mansouri et al.³ reported that only 10% of treated sites showed a 50% improvement in papillary fill at 3 months, while 43% of the sites demonstrated over 50% improvement by 6 months. Similarly, Abdelraouf et al.⁹ (2019) found that the mean reduction in the surface area of black triangles using HA was $36.5 \pm 24.4\%$ at 3 months and $45.0 \pm 28.5\%$ at 6 months from baseline, indicating progressive results over time.

Platelet-Rich Plasma (PRP) and Platelet-Rich Fibrin (PRF) are autologous blood-derived products enriched with growth factors that significantly support tissue regeneration. Notably, Sharma P et al.⁹ and Ahila et al.¹⁰ observed substantial improvements in interdental papilla reconstruction using a surgical approach incorporating PRF membranes, with encouraging outcomes at both 3- and 6-month intervals.

Despite PRP’s widespread use, concerns remain due to the addition of anticoagulants during preparation, which help maintain its liquid form for easier mixing with biomaterials. Conversely, early PRF formulations lacked a liquid phase, as growth factors were primarily entrapped within the fibrin mesh of the membrane.

To address these limitations, a new formulation called Injectable PRF (I-PRF) was developed, eliminating both anticoagulants and fibrin matrix. This innovation was driven by Ghanaati et al.¹¹ introduction of low-speed centrifugation, which increases the concentration of regenerative cells and enhances biological activity.

I-PRF, derived through low-speed centrifugation, preserves high concentrations of platelets, leukocytes, and growth factors like VEGF, PDGF, and TGF- β 1.⁵ These biomolecules play key roles in promoting angiogenesis, cell proliferation, and extracellular matrix remodelling critical for tissue regeneration and wound healing. As an autologous product, I-PRF minimizes the risk of immune reactions and outperforms avascular materials like hyaluronic acid and xenografts, which lack the vascular support needed for effective tissue regeneration.

Furthermore, I-PRF is prepared using anticoagulant-free tubes and gradually forms a fibrin clot after injection. This clot acts as a dynamic hydrogel, potentially encapsulating cells and allowing a sustained release of growth factors for up to 10 days, thereby enhancing gingival fibroblast activity and promoting continued tissue healing.⁵

This study evaluated the effectiveness of I-PRF in interdental papilla reconstruction in the esthetic area. Participants in the study were between 18 and 45 years old to eliminate the influence of age-related changes on papillary recession. Only individuals with good oral hygiene were included to avoid the detrimental effects of poor hygiene on tissue healing,¹² as inadequate oral care can contribute to periodontitis, a known cause of papillary loss.

A prerequisite for inclusion was the presence of a contact point between adjacent teeth, which is essential for successful papilla reconstruction, as highlighted in the study by Tarnow et al.¹³ Additionally, participants who were pregnant or breastfeeding were excluded to eliminate hormonal influences on gingival tissues.¹⁴

Regarding the Modified Gingival Index (MGI), a statistically significant improvement was observed post-treatment. This outcome is attributed to the reinforcement of proper oral hygiene practices and consistent oral care instructions provided during treatment and follow-up visits.

In the present case series, i-PRF was administered at twelve sites in four periodontally and systemically healthy individuals with Class I or II papilla loss. Clinical assessment after three months revealed 100% papillary fill in four sites, 75% in three, and 66.6% in four, and 50% in the remaining one. These findings suggest that i-PRF can enhance soft tissue volume and aesthetic appearance in papilla-deficient sites with predictable outcomes.

Similar results were reported by Puri et al.,¹⁵ who observed 100% fill in three sites and notable improvements in the remaining after six months of I-PRF application. In contrast, a study by Thawab Al Salkhadi et al.¹⁶ reported no statistically significant changes in papillary dimensions after three months of I-PRF treatment, indicating variability in outcomes across different clinical settings.

Thus although the results are encouraging, larger randomized controlled trials with extended follow-up are necessary to validate the long-term efficacy of I-PRF.

In conclusion, I-PRF is a safe, minimally invasive, and biologically active treatment for interdental papilla reconstruction, offering a viable alternative to surgical or synthetic options in the management of black triangles.

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